

Synthesis and Study of Flavan-4 β -ols

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Flavanones of selective hydroxyl pattern have been reduced with sodium borohydride in presence of boric acid. The product, in every case, is shown to be a quasi axial flavan-4 β -ol. These compounds are quite stable in presence of 3% HCl in glacial acetic acid, but undergo polymerisation under more rigorous conditions. The action of POCl₃-pyridine is shown to effect partial dehydration.

Catechins and hydroxyflavan-3,4-diols (Leucoanthocyanidins) are known to give rise to tannins by polymerisation, caused by protonic attack or by enzymes. Freudenberg¹ put forward a scheme of self-condensation in which a protonic attack on a flavan produced a 2-carbonium ion which reacted with C₆ or C₈ in another molecule of flavan. He also suggested another probable path² of self-condensation through the 4-hydroxyl in a flavan-4-ol to give rise to dimers, the point of attachment being at C₆ or C₈ of another flavan. Roux and Paulus³ suggest that of the two, 4-hydroxyl is more reactive in flavan-3,4-diols and these are much faster in polymerisation than the catechins^{4,5}. There is not much experimental evidence, however, so far recorded on the reactivity of flavan-4-ols.

During the course of our work on *Citrus mitis* Blanco⁶, a number of flavanones of selective hydroxyl pattern became available and therefore it was proposed to synthesise and study the corresponding flavan-4-ols. We were also drawn to their study by a very significant reaction between flavanones and NaBH₄, discovered by Pew⁷ and later extensively used by Hrowitz⁸ as a colour reaction for the detection of flavanones and their glycosides in citrus fruits.

Flavan-4-ols have been synthesised and studied recently^{9,10}. It has been shown by Bognar *et al.*¹⁰ that reduction of flavanones (I) using Pt-H₂ produces a quasi axial flavan-4-ol (III) and Al-Hg, the corresponding quasi equatorial isomer (II). Among other reagents, Raney Ni-ethanol, ammoniacal titanous chloride, and LiAlH₄ are also known to give rise to quasi axial flavan-4-ols (III)¹¹. But the reduction of flavanones with NaBH₄ has not been studied extensively. Pew⁷ was the first to use NaBH₄ to reduce 6-allyl-8-methoxy- and 6-allyl-8, 3',4'-trimethoxy-flavanones; but he did not record the steric con-

1. Freudenberg and Weinges, "Progress in Chemistry of Organic Natural Products", 1958, **16**, 7.
2. Freudenberg, *Exper.*, 1960, **16**, 101.
3. *Biochem. J.*, 1961, **80**, 476.
4. Roux, *J. Amer. Leather Chem. Assoc.*, 1950, **54**, 614.
5. Weinges, *Annalen*, 1958, **615**, 203.
6. Sastry and Row, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **15**, 111.
7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2831.
8. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 1733.
9. Joshi and Kulkarni, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 753.
10. *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 135.

figurations of the products obtained. More recently, Kashikar and Kulkarni¹² used this reagent and obtained 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4 β -ol.

(I)

(II)

(III)

In the present investigation, NaBH₄ was added to an ethanolic solution of the flavanone in presence of boric acid. Neutralisation with acetic acid precipitated flavan-4-ols (Table I) as colorless crystalline compounds in very good yields (80-85%).

TABLE I

Methoxy-flavan-4-ols.	M.P.	Colour with H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.).	Colour with HCl (conc.).	Colour of flavanone in H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.). ⁴
1. 6,4'-Dimethoxy-Acetate	148-49° 127-28°	Intense violet-red	Blue, green-yellow	Bright orange-red
2. 6,3',4'-Trimethoxy-Acetate	140-42° 110-11°	Intense blue, fades rapidly	Blue	Red
3. 6,7,3',4'-Tetramethoxy-Acetate	144,46° 118-20°	Intense blue	Blue-purple-violet	Orange
4. 7,8,3',4'-Tetramethoxy-Acetate	120-21° 95-96°	Carmine-red with blue	Violet, fades	"
5. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxy- ¹¹	130-38°	Intense violet	Violet	Orange
6. 5,6,7,8,3',4'-Hexa-methoxy-flavone	95-96°	Intense blue, dichroic red	Reddish blue	"

The reduction of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone¹¹ either with NaBH₄ or LiAlH₄ produced the same flavan-4-ol. The latter reagent is definitely shown¹⁰ to produce quasi axial flavan-4-ols. It is therefore concluded that NaBH₄ also produces the quasi axial alcohols. That, indeed, is the case is shown by the reactivity of the flavan-4-ols under study.

The flavan-4-ols (Table I) are all colorless compounds giving rise to stable acetates, even in presence of 3% HCl in glacial acetic acid at 60° for 15 mins. (I.R. spectrum: 1745 cm⁻¹ for acetate). When the reaction was repeated for a longer time, invariably tannin-like uncrystallisable products were obtained with indefinite melting points.

The action of POCl₃-pyridine was, however, indefinite. With 6,3',4'-trimethoxy- and 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxy-flavan-4-ols, mixtures were obtained. Separation by crystallisation or by chromatography on alumina was very tedious and ineffective. But analysis of close melting fractions indicated partial dehydration in both cases.

11. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, **18B**, 418.

12. Kulkarni and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1957, **16B**, 240.

Joshi and Kulkarni⁹ reported that the acetates of equatorial flavan-4-ols were hydrolysed faster than the axial acetates. This formation of stable acetates with 3% HCl in glacial acetic acid emphasises their stability and confirms the axial conformation in the flavan-4-ols under study.

Citromitin (5,6,7,8,3',4'-hexamethoxyflavanone)⁶ differs significantly from the rest. Reduction with NaBH₄ provided a compound which did not afford an acetate, showing the absence of free hydroxyl. Its analysis also indicates dehydration; the compound may therefore be regarded as the corresponding flavene which may require further confirmation.

A reaction that deserves mention is the exhibition of colours when these flavan-4-ols are treated with H₂SO₄ (conc.) or with HCl in glacial acetic acid or in ethanol. Intense blue, violet, or purple colours are obtained; these colours differ from those of anthocyanidins (red to reddish orange or pink) and may indicate a profound change of the flavan-4-ols in strongly acid medium. Roux and Paulus³ regarded this colour reaction as characteristic of flavan-4-ols and used it for detection of this group in tannins.

EXPERIMENTAL

6,4'-Dimethoxyflavan-4-ol.—A general method for the preparation of flavan-quasi-axial-4-ols is recorded below.

A solution of 6,4'-dimethoxyflavanone¹³ (500 mg.) and boric acid (120 mg.) in rectified spirit (40 ml) was treated cautiously with sodium borohydride (160 mg.). A white solid separated within 10 minutes; the mixture was kept at room temperature. After 3 hours the solvent was distilled and the residue dissolved in water. The clear solution was acidified with very dilute acetic acid when a white solid was obtained. It was crystallised from methanol as colorless needles, m.p. 148-49°, yield 415 mg. (Found: C, 71.29; H, 6.45. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.31; H, 6.30%).

The *acetate* (pyridine-Ac₂O) crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 127-28°. (Found: C, 69.88; H, 6.45. C₁₉H₂₀O₅ requires C, 69.50; H, 6.09%).

6,3'-Dimethoxyflavan-4-ol.—A solution of 6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavanone¹⁴ (500 mg.) was reduced with sodium borohydride (120 mg.) in presence of boric acid (100 mg.). After 3 hours at room temperature, the flavan-4-ol was separated as before and crystallised from methanol as colorless needles, m.p. 140-42°, yield 405 mg. (Found: C, 67.14; H, 6.52. C₁₈H₂₀O₅ · H₂O requires C, 66.62; H, 6.46%).

The *acetyl* derivative (Ac₂O-pyridine) crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 110-11°. (Found: C, 67.39; H, 6.24. C₂₀H₂₂O₆ requires C, 67.04; H, 6.15%).

6,7,3',4'-Tetramethoxyflavan-4-ol.—Reduction of 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavanone¹⁵ (200 mg.) by sodium borohydride in presence of boric acid yielded 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavan-4-ol (162 mg.) which separated from ethanol as colorless flakes, m.p. 144-46°. (Found: C, 65.45; H, 6.07. C₁₉H₂₂O₆ requires C, 65.89; H, 6.36%).

13. Kostanocki and Stoppani, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 781.

14. *Idem*, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 779.

15. Geissman and Clinton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 697.

The 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxy-4-acetoxyflavan came out as colorless needles from aqueous acetone, m.p. 118-20°. (Found: C, 65.24; H, 6.42. $C_{21}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 64.80; H, 6.19%).

7,8,3',4'-Tetramethoxyflavan-4-ol.—7,8,3',4'-Tetramethoxyflavanone¹⁶ (400 mg.) was reduced with $NaBH_4$ to the corresponding flavan-4-ol (335 mg.) as before. It crystallised from methanol in the form of colorless flakes, m.p. 120-21°. (Found: C, 65.68; H, 6.30. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.89; H, 6.36%).

The acetyl derivative (Ac₂O-pyridine) crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 64.92; H, 6.21. $C_{21}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 64.80; H, 6.19%).

6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4-ol.—The reduction of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone¹⁷ (300 mg.) was carried out with $NaBH_4$ to the corresponding flavan-4-ol (255 mg.) in the usual way. It crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 136-38°.

Reduction of Citromitin.—Citromitin⁷ (200 mg.) was reduced in presence of boric acid by means of $NaBH_4$ in the usual way to the corresponding flavan-4-ol (125 mg.). It came out from methanol as colorless flakes, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 63.80; H, 6.27. $C_{21}H_{24}O_7$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 63.48; H, 6.29%). Acetylation with pyridine-Ac₂O gave back the original compound.

Action of 3% HCl-Glacial Acetic Acid.—6,3',4'-Trimethoxyflavan-4-ol (200 mg.) was dissolved in a mixture of 3% HCl in acetic acid, warmed at 60° for 15 minutes, and finally kept at room temperature. After 3 hours, the solution was poured into water (25 ml). The white precipitate was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 110-12°, yield 145 mg. (I.R. spectrum: $1754cm^{-1}$ for acetate), undepressed with the acetate obtained from pyridine-Ac₂O method.

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